

MISCONCEPTIONS IN SCIENCE LEARNING VIS-À-VIS CRITICAL THINKING

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Abstract

Despite several efforts for improving science education, learners at various levels, often retain intuitive yet incorrect beliefs about core scientific principles such as misconceptions related to scientific concepts in physics, chemistry, and biology. The researches highlight that misconceptions arise not because lack of information but often due to learners' preconceived notions, experiential learning, mass media exposure, resource materials, internet, false reasoning, teachers' and their own cognitive biases, etc. While, critical thinking helps learners move beyond rote learning by engaging them in processes that challenge their initial assumptions through evidence-based reasoning, hypothesis testing, and logical analysis. In this regard, this paper explores that critical thinking as a pivotal tool for addressing and transforming such misconceptions into accurate scientific understanding among learners. By enhancing critical thinking among learners, teachers can make them to question, analyse, and evaluate scientific information more rigorously, which is essential for overcoming misconceptions. Furthermore, critical thinking strategies in the science classroom such as analysing arguments, inductive and deductive reasoning, promoting inquiry and problem-based learning, and reflective thinking enables learners to recognize and rectify their own misconceptions. Moreover, promoting a culture of inquiry and skepticism encourages learners to approach scientific problems with open-mindedness and resilience, enhancing their long-term cognitive adaptability. Therefore, this paper also discusses the need for science curricula and teacher training programmes to prioritize critical thinking as an integral component in combating misconceptions. Teachers equipped with critical thinking skills, can not only address immediate misunderstandings among their learners but also empower them in assimilating complex scientific concepts appropriately throughout their educational endeavours. The findings of this paper entail a shift in pedagogical strategies, emphasizing the importance of critical thinking in transforming science education from fact acquisition to concept mastery, thereby developing a generation of scientifically literate and critically engaged thinkers.

Keywords: *Misconceptions, Science Learning, Critical Thinking*

Introduction

Science is all about facts. It basically focuses on the pursuit of a profound comprehension of facts, events, and, natural phenomena cannot be completed without a proper understanding of it. Most people today believe that learners bring to science classes certain preconceived conceptions and ideas that are deeply ingrained in their thought processes. The terms misconceptions (Helm, 1980), preconceptions (Novak, 1977), and alternative frameworks (Driven, 1981) have been used to describe students' ideas

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that differ from those typically acknowledged by the scientific community. There is ample evidence in the literature that in the secondary level, learners frequently have misconceptions about concepts like gravity (Dogina & Dah, 2023), season, big bang (Cardinot & Fairfield, 2021), force, motion, chemical bonding and cell biology. Different types of factors that cause misconceptions among the individuals related to internet, learners' prior knowledge, textbooks, teacher, parents, prerequisite knowledge of learners, a negligence and assumptions behind a rule, an interference of learnt materials, an uncritical acceptance of incorrect information and false reasoning. Despite of that diagnostic tests, interview and tests consisting of open-ended questions, concept map and multiple-choice tests used for identify the misconceptions. Addressing these misconceptions is crucial for effective science learning. Understanding their origins and prevalence allows teachers to design targeted interventions that promote conceptual change, ensuring learners, and developing accurate and coherent scientific knowledge.

Furthermore, the twentieth century has witnessed a preliminary level of science even in universities. In order to incorporate general science in school curriculum, Government of India appointed a number of commissions and committees to develop curriculum, textbook and study materials. The report of Secondary Education Commission (1952) recommended general science as a compulsory subject in high school and higher secondary classes. In line with the earlier theories opined by different educationist and thinkers, science learning relies on constructivist teaching approach. Constructivist teaching has caused a paradigm shift in education from behaviourism to cognitive theory. The contributions of Dewey (1938), Montessori (1966), Piaget (1972), Bruner (1960) and Vygotsky (1978) provided the necessary framework for constructivism.

Although Bruner (1960) suggests that teaching science is to facilitate learners in developing problem-solving competencies at intermediate level. The teacher must know how to facilitate a positive learning experience including the context for actual problem solving to all learners. It also promotes the learner's knowledge development, critical thinking, logical ability, skills for seeing relationships, analysing an unfamiliar situation, synthesizing different ideas in a given problem, divergent thinking, interpreting a concept and drawing inferences. Thus, the quality of science teaching should be raised from promoting basic principles, to develop problem-solving and analytical skills and to promote the spirit of enquiry through experimentation and accurate observation.

While for developing critical thinking, Bloom's Taxonomy can help learners analyse information critically and develop critical thinking skills among the learners. It can also help teachers to encourage their learners to think at higher levels. According to Edward Glaser, critical thinking depends on three things such as attitude, knowledge and skill which help in developing logical inquiry and reasoning. Also, different policy documents focus at developing 21st century skills based on cultural and historical perspective, prioritising professionalism in education including work and life and enforcing critical thinking among learners. However, critical thinking is believed to include the different components such as, skills of analyzing arguments through inductive or deductive reasoning, judging or evaluating,

making decisions and solving the problem. Also, it helps learners move beyond rote learning by involving them in processes that challenge their initial assumptions through evidence-based reasoning, and logical analysis. Thus, this paper explores common misconceptions and their impact on learning, and strategies for overcoming through developing critical thinking among learners.

Factors causing misconceptions in science learning

Misconceptions is the idea that provides an incorrect understanding of such ideas, objects or events that was constructed based on person's experience (Martin, Sexton, & Gerlovich, 2002), preconceived notions, non-scientific beliefs, naïve theories, mixed conceptions or conceptual misunderstanding. (Hanuscin), alternate conceptions (Van den Berg & Grosheide, 1993; Dykstra, Boyle, & Monarch 1992; Heller & Finley, 1992; Arnaudin & Mintzes, 1985).

In addition, websites contain incorrect information and inadequate knowledge which can cause various misconceptions. Students join school with prerequisite knowledge which create misconceptions among them and their progress is possible through the help of education. Other sources of misconceptions are related to resource materials, media and teachers (Alagumalai, 2005), learner's prior knowledge was the most important variable to be successful in learning science (Bilgin and Uzuntiryaki, 2003), misunderstanding of a concept due to an inadequate prerequisite knowledge, a negligence on the conditions and assumptions behind a rule, an interference of learnt materials, an uncritical acceptance of incorrect information and a wrong deduction due to false reasoning (Driver et al., 1994).

Furthermore, Diagnostic tests (Wu & Tsai, 2007), interview and tests consisting of open-ended questions used for determining misconceptions (Eshach & Schwartz, 2006), multiple choice tests (Peterson, Treagust, & Garnett, 1989; Taber 1999a), were used for determining misconceptions.

Misconceptions in science learning: Some examples

In science learning, the content related to gravity, seasons and big-bang theory (Cardinot & Fairfield, 2021), heat and temperature (Fenditasari & Istiyono, 2020), understanding of waves (Caleon & Subramanian, 2020), hydrostatic pressure (Wijaya & Muhardjito, 2016), heat and temperature (Alwan 2011) and energy (Boyes & Stanisstreet, 1991) were also seen misconception among the learners.

Along with, a number of misconceptions were about shape of earth and position of sun, earth and moon (Costu et al., 2022); concepts of relativity among students and the major reason of misconception due to the teaching method, the available materials, and instructor affirmation (Listianingrum et al., 2022), salt solubility (Izzati & Rochmah, 2020), chemical equilibrium (Jusniar et al., 2020), solubility equilibrium, covalent bonds, ionic bonds, hydrogen bonds, molecule geometry, action notion in elements, chemical equilibrium, dissolution, electrolyze, and batteries (Üce & Ceyhan, 2019) and acid-base (Mughtar, 2012), virus and Covid-19, mitosis and meiosis (Luwoye et al., 2021), genetics, ecology, botany and zoology (Rogayan & Albino, 2019), cell biology (Hala et al., 2019), and adaptations, biosphere, ecosystem, habitat, biomass and biodiversity (Oberoi, 2017) were also seen misconceptions among learners.

Critical thinking and associated skills

The educational objectives set out by Benjamin Bloom would provide as the foundation of critical thinking definition (Bloom et.al., 1956). The original set of objectives, commonly known as the Bloom's Taxonomy, which primarily refer to different levels of thinking that should be developed during the course of any educational endeavour. Also, Anderson et.al. in 2001 revised the Bloom's Taxonomy into remembering, understanding, applying, analysing, evaluating, and creating which deals with knowledge and cognitive dimensions of thinking, since these theoretical foundations provide a systematic, progressive road map to the more complex thinking that needs to be mastered in the long run. Elder and Paul's (2008) discussion on critical thinking is the most relevant association of aspirational standards and virtues with the process of thinking. Also, these association of standards and practices takes critical thinking into different domains of metacognition, thinking about thinking. Together with the standards and virtues of critical thinking that acquires an in-built affective dimension which separated from the cognitive dimensions focused on by Bloom et.al. (1956) and Anderson et.al. (2001).

Furthermore, critical thinking skills encompass the ability to interpret, analyse, evaluate, explain, and self-regulate the ideas. Also, the dispositions include being "inquisitive, well-informed, trustful of reason, open-minded, flexible, fair-minded in evaluation, honest in facing personal biases, prudent in making judgments, willing to reconsider, clear about issues, orderly in complex matters, diligent in seeking relevant information, reasonable in the selection of criteria, focused in inquiry, and persistent in seeking results (Facione, 2013).

Significance of critical thinking for science learning

Critical thinking plays an important role for development and growth of learners (Zahran ,2001). It help the individuals to access the correct information, which results in exploration of knowledge. The development of critical thinking skills is necessary to search for truthful, useful and valuable information from internet of different subject. Although, it encourages spirit of inquiry, research and non-acceptance of facts without enough investigation (AI- Ghadouni, Abdullah Bin Mohamed, 2021).

Furthermore, critical thinking is related to misconceptions on science learning revealed that when the misconceptions are high, learners critical thinking skills will be low and vice versa. The role of critical thinking as a pivotal tool for addressing and transforming such misconceptions into accurate scientific understanding among learners. (Yolviansyah, Fauziah & Siregar, Juita & Maison, Maison, 2022).

Moreover, critical thinking is the foundation for developing a pathway for nature of science learning. For developing future citizens' understandings through science learning is considered essential for fostering scientific literacy, move beyond rote learning by engaging them in processes that challenge their initial assumptions through evidence-based reasoning, hypothesis testing, and logical analysis (American Association for the Advancement of Science, 1993; Laugksch, 2000).

Strategies for enhancing critical thinking in science classrooms

Different strategies that science teachers employ for facilitating critical thinking among learners inside the classroom enable them to enjoy the process of learning which involves analysing information, inductive and deductive reasoning, promoting inquiry and problem-based learning, and reflective thinking. It helps the learners in reducing alternative concepts (Choy & Cheah, 2009). Along with, a metacognitive strategy (Valle et al., 2020) and effective in activating prior knowledge highlighting misconceptions and promoting reflection in learning which provides a foundation for the assimilation of new knowledge and improving critical thinking through increased engagement, making predictions, arousing curiosity, comparing beliefs. Also, the modelling of the strategy is effective for developing critical thinking because learners will learn from teachers who share their thinking (Calo, 2011).

Furthermore, learning cycle text, conceptual change texts (Chambers & Andre, 1997); hands on activities, computer supported in class presentations, analogies, exposing event method, text structures, conceptual change approach, promoting a culture of inquiry and skepticism encourage learners to approach scientific problems with open-mindedness and resilience, enhancing their long-term cognitive adaptability. (Brown, 1992); generic teaching of critical thinking (Ennis, 1989), subject or content specific teaching of critical thinking (McPeck, 1990), immersion, infusion, and mixed methods of teaching critical thinking (Ennis, 2011) can be used as remedial strategies for reducing misconceptions. Moreover, a shift in pedagogical strategies, emphasizing the importance of critical thinking in transforming science education from fact acquisition to concept mastery, thereby developing a generation of scientifically literate and critically engaged thinkers that leads toward developing critical thinking and eliminating misconceptions among learners (Ennis, 2011).

Science curricula and teacher training for critical thinking

Learner's response to critical thinking depends on how teachers understand and think critically inside the classroom. Critical thinking is not developed, when learners are not actively involved in classroom activities, passive behaviour that results from teacher-centredness. Proper understanding of teachers towards learners' needs and thereby developing content aids to critical thinking (Dwee et al., 2016).

Furthermore, with a focussed approach to critical thinking among learners, teachers can make them to question, analyse, and evaluate scientific information more rigorously, which is essential for overcoming misconceptions. However, teachers' understanding related to the importance of teaching critical thinking throughout the curriculum including the science curricula per se plays a crucial role. Also, the use of effective teaching strategies on teacher training programmes as an integral component in combating misconceptions and developing critical thinking among learners could be instrumental in developing critical thinking among learners (Ennis, 2011).

The way forward

The study has implications to different realms. It would help in eliminating the misconceptions in science learning leading to the appropriate progress and betterment of learners, which in its turn, helps

in developing scientific temper and encouraging reflective practices among learners. In case of the presence of misconceptions as discussed in this paper would imply that the teachers should anticipate prevailing misconceptions among learners regarding each topic, and consequently, appropriate steps may be taken for development of the correct concept among them. Additionally, there are various sources of misconceptions, including the method of teaching that they employ in classrooms. This implies that teachers must be careful enough while introducing science related terminologies and definitions.

Moreover, eliminating misconceptions among students will develop awareness among science teachers and other stakeholders. For developing critical thinking, appropriate teaching strategies to be incorporated by teachers for learners' future, ensuring better science learning among them and prioritizing the same in curricula. Critical thinking has to be conceived an integral component by every stakeholder, in combating misconceptions. It would pave the way for better conceptual understanding of facts among learners bridging the existing gap, and, also would develop scientific temper among them.

Conclusion

Critical thinking is an effective tool for correcting or eliminating misconceptions in science learning. It enables learners to challenge existing misconceptions by analysing arguments, inductive and deductive reasoning, inquiry and problem-based learning, and incorporating reflective thinking. Also, this skill helps learners in questioning their preconceived notions and accept scientifically proven information. Studies have highlighted that traditional rote-learning methods may reinforce misconceptions, while inquiry-based and constructivist approaches encourage critical thinking and help address misunderstandings. However, learners benefit a lot when they actively explore and resolve conflicts between their misconceptions and scientific principles. Moreover, teachers and other stakeholders play a pivotal role in identifying misconceptions, fostering critical thinking, and creating opportunities for learners to test and refine their ideas through evidence and reasoning based learning. Also, interdisciplinary connections between science and other disciplines can enhance critical thinking skills and address misconceptions by exposing learners to multiple frameworks for understanding complex ideas. Moreover, proper implementation of different plan and policy of government helps for developing scientific temper among the learners through science curriculum.

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